

Aspects of the conservation and ecology of the Great Barrier Reef

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Queensland Littoral Society Newsletter (No. 29, November-December 1968) pp 1-7
DOI 10.5281/zenodo.5698993

(An address given to a General Meeting of the Queensland Littoral Society, 14th October 1968)

Man is a dominant species. We do not live in just a portion of our environment; we attempt to occupy all of it. Despite this, we are becoming increasingly concerned with conserving our environment. The two most politically persuasive reasons for conservation are to save areas for future, more advantageous exploitation, and protection of our health. As far as the Barrier Reef is concerned, the most persuasive argument is that the immediate gain of a few individuals cannot be balanced against the advantages future generations of Australians will gain from the exploitation for scientific and tourist uses of an intact Barrier Reef.

We must use economic arguments because they have great weight even with those interested in immediate exploitation. We can say to these people we accept all of your premises and still it is to your advantage to conserve the Reef. Since I am talking to a group of conservationists who are particularly familiar with the practical arguments for conservation, I shall try to raise some more general questions, and in doing this I hope to give a little more of an idea of what I think the Barrier Reef is. Man seems to have the need to conquer, occupy and alter every part of this globe. It is time to examine this need and ask whether it is desirable to follow this will-to-conquer unquestioningly. Australia is lucky in having so few people, but some people seem to feel guilty about it. There is widespread opinion that development is desirable regardless of the cost. Because the Reef is so unique and well-known it is regarded as a prime target for development. It doesn't seem to occur to anyone that the main reason the Reef is unique and well-known is because it hasn't been interfered with.

The great potential use of the Reef for man is to give him an idea of the beauty and variety which is possible in this world. This means development of the scientific and tourist potential of the Reef. There should be greater opportunity for everyone to see the Reef at close hand. This does not mean catering to those who want to take away a piece of the Reef or to those most interested in the indoor entertainment luxury hotels provide. More laboratories should be built on the Reef and the existing laboratory at Heron Island should be developed. The scientific effort should be aimed at finding out what the Reef is rather than what products might be taken from it. As the French anthropologist Levi-Strauss has said in another context, perhaps it is too late to preserve this variety but at least we can try to preserve a memory of it. Supposing some chemical compound were found as a cure for cancer which could not be synthesised and tons of coral were required to produce even small quantities of it. There is no question that if this happened the Reef would be destroyed. Already if it were a choice between oil or the Reef many would prefer the oil.

I have said man is a dominant animal. He seeks bulk commodities for his use and the only bulk commodities of the Reef are whole categories of plants and animals. We do not talk of

saving single species such as the herring, the blue whale, the red kangaroo, or the redwood. We talk of saving the *fish* or saving the *coral*. The fish and coral are endangered by mining of substrate, itself the result of biological processes operating over many thousands of years. Recently, a lot has been said about whether the *coral* would be destroyed during limestone mining; of course, *all* the coral wouldn't be destroyed. Coral occurs throughout the world at all latitudes. Near Beaufort, North Carolina where I worked for some time, there is quite a nice man-made reef with *one* species of coral. There is coral in Moreton Bay *and* near Sydney and Adelaide. At depths of up to 600 metres off North Carolina, and at great depths off most coasts, coral banks are found. You have all heard of the beautiful coral reefs of the Caribbean. Only 35 species of coral belonging to 26 genera have been described from these reefs. In contrast, 240 species of coral in 52 genera are known from the Pacific. Probably most of these species occur on the Barrier Reef but we will have to wait for the results of the first quantitative collections along the whole reef made recently by Woodhead of the Heron Island Research Station. Most of the species of plants and animals on the Reef are rare and they specialise on some very small portion of the environment. Perhaps already the pesticides and fertiliser from the cane fields are allowing some of the more tolerant species to become abundant at the expense of great numbers of rare species less adapted to the changing environment. Since many of the reef species live a very long time, we might not find out which species have been destroyed for a generation when the present adults die out. For example, fertilisers or pesticides would first affect the planktonic larvae of many reef species. If the larvae couldn't survive, then whether the adults could stand the pollution would be irrelevant.

We may divide plants and animals into two general categories. On the one hand, there are the dominant or opportunistic species which are not typical of the reef, and on the other, the rare specialist species which *are* common on the reef. By opportunistic species I mean those which live a short time and can increase in numbers rapidly. These are the weeds of *both* the plant and animal kingdoms. The extreme examples of these kinds of species follow man because he makes the sort of environment which is favourable for them. Such species are flies, rats, and cockroaches. One of the most common insects at Heron Island is the cockroach, one of the most common vertebrates is the rat.

Most of what we know about biology is based on dominant or opportunistic animals which survive well in the laboratory. Embryologists work with sea urchins, chickens, pigs, and frogs. Most physiologists work with mice, rats, dogs, cattle, rabbits, or humans. Geneticists work with moulds, fruit flies, and mice. Geologists interested in palaeontology study the dominant species which have a high probability of being preserved. This is why we have so much difficulty in tracing evolutionary history from the fossil record. One of the three founders of modern evolutionary theory, Haldane, has said that the greatest evolutionary advances have come from rare specialised species. Ecologists have either studied the laboratory animals mentioned or have worked in areas near the older and larger universities of temperate regions. More recently, ecologists have been interested in tropical areas because the only way an ecologist can study the effects of the environment over long periods of time is to compare areas. The clearest comparisons come from comparing temperate regions with the tropics. In doing this we are faced with many problems.

You have heard that with regard to the plants and animals of the Barrier Reef we are very ignorant. I will use an example of the group I know most about. Scientific expeditions to coral reefs have found very few polychaetes (marine worms). The Royal Society Expedition to the

Ellice Islands [now Tuvalu] at the turn of the century found five of these worms. The 1928-29 Great Barrier Reef Expedition found 46 species at Low Isles. In the extensive studies done in the Northern Marshall Islands up to 1954 they found 100 species: 72 species from Eniwetok, 41 from Bikini and 20 from Rongelap. I have taken over 100 species from a single head of coral at Heron Island. I do not know what many of those species are and they are likely to be undescribed. No one has tried to count all the animals from a single metre square on the Reef let alone animals on a whole reef or several reefs.

From systematic descriptions of plants and animals from such stable areas as the oceanic islands of Aldabra and the Galapagos, the ancient lakes of Baikal, Tanganyika and Ohrid, the rainforests scattered around the world, and coral reefs, ecologists have realised that some different processes are going on than from what we have become familiar with in temperate areas. We may ask why these environments have so many species. I think the reason is that the plants and animals in all these environments are more specialised in their requirements. Over very long periods of time each species has been able to survive without having to eat a great variety of foods or the need to spread out over a large area. If each species occupies only a little part of the environment, then there is room for more species. Since these species are so specialised, they cannot withstand sudden environmental changes. The plants and animals of all the places I have mentioned are threatened. The Soviet Union has built a pulp mill next to Lake Baikal and is pumping effluent into the lake, a procedure which is likely to kill most of the 200 species of amphipods which have evolved in this lake and nowhere else. Most of you know that nearly all, if not all, the virgin rainforest of Australia is gone. Recently the island of Aldabra was threatened with destruction by the building of a British air base. Only the combination of economic problems at home and the outcry of scientists from all over the world prevented the base from being built.

A lot of what is said about the Barrier Reef is either not true or based on no evidence. Many say that animals from the Reef can be used to save people in some of the poorer Asian countries from starving in the coming decade. This is not so. Most animals of the Reef live a long time and reproduce slowly so that a large fishery could not be sustained. From studies of native populations of atolls, it is estimated that two acres of reef would be required to support one man. With the sort of effort used in the North Sea, the Reef could be fished out in a very few years.

Growth rates of coral are used to predict how quickly coral will grow back following kills. These growth rates may *not* be relevant as even the *fastest* growing species may become extinct if conditions are unfavourable. *No one* suggests that the growth rates of kangaroos be used to determine whether they will increase or not. Killing any individual of the long-living, slow-producing species of the reef increases the likelihood that the species will not survive. Various people talk about minimum self-sustaining areas of the Reef. Parks have been proposed as self-sustaining areas. We do not know what a self-sustaining area is. Not only may the whole Barrier Reef be an interrelated complex, but all the reefs of the Pacific may be interrelated. For example, the Barrier Reef may be necessary to sustain the fauna of the Pacific atolls. This possibility has been raised by the work of Scheltema who has shown that the larvae of coral and other species can travel back and forth across the Atlantic. We are mystified by the fact that a species such as the Crown-of-Thorns starfish may be abundant in only a small area of one reef and then not be found on surrounding reefs. We underestimate the ability of species to specialise in stable environments. We speak of the balance of nature, but there may be no

balance, only individual species which may become extinct, and result in the extinction of other species, if interfered with.

Among stable ecological systems, the Barrier Reef is unique. Ladd has indicated that it may be the only reef in which the major reef-building process is the result of coral growth rather than reef-building algae. It is not just another reef it is *the* reef, against which all generalisations concerning coral reefs must be tested. All the adjectives ecologists use to describe reefs may be applied in the superlative. As a system it is the most diverse; in terms of energy, it is the most efficient with the slowest turnover of any environment. Species are likely to have the greatest range of life spans including the longest living animals found anywhere. Species may at the same time have the widest dispersal and the lowest density. We know nothing about the variety of genetic systems or developmental systems in these species. We know little about their physiology. We are only just beginning to describe the patches within patches of animals which occur on the Reef. Adequate description will involve statistical techniques not yet devised. The only analogous problem is the description of galaxies in the universe.

This brings us back to my central point. There are two kinds of human experience which enable man to partially understand his position in nature. One is looking up at the stars and I think the other is swimming out over the edge of the Reef. Too few people have been able to see the Reef, and none has adequately described the experience. In the future the reefs may be doomed but if we can increase our efforts now at least the memory of this experience may be preserved.

[Publisher's note: This is a manual transcription from an archival copy of the Newsletter copy-edited by R. H. Bradbury on 30 October 2021]

Republished on Zenodo, November 2021
DOI 10.5281/zenodo.5698993